

Table 1 continued.

Selection	RTV % ^a	Grade
IR32843-92-2-2-3	40	6
IR32851-87-2-3-1	56	7
IR34631-79-2-2-3	46	7
IR35293-125-3-2-3	15	4
IR35366-28-3-1-2-2	54	7
IR35366-90-3-2-1-2	0	0
IR35546-17-3-1-3	36	6
IR35546-33-2-2-3	33	6
IR37865-29-3-1-3	10	3
IR39357-91-3-2-3	10	3
IR39357-133-3-2-2-3	60	7
IR39379-99-2-3-2-3	69	4
IR39385-20-1-2-1-1	25	5
IR39385-124-3-3-2-3	18	4
IR41985-111-3-2-2	80	8
IR42015-83-2-2-2	38	6
IR39379-190-2-2-3-1	17	4
IR39422-18-1-2-2	75	8
IR25604-99-1-3-2-2	18	4
IR39422-19-3-3-3-3	60	7
IR39423-124-3-3-1	46	7
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	54	7
IR28150-84-3-3-2	21	5
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	46	7
IR28224-3-2-3-2	72	8
IR28228-28-1-3-3-2	29	5
IR28228-119-2-3-1-1	18	4
IR29723-143-3-2-1	53	7
IR31836-46-1-3-1	62	8
IR32453-93-3-3-1-3	40	6
IR32720-138-2-1-1-2	70	8
IR34583-22-1-2	62	8
IR39326-9-2-2-3	62	8
IR39334-31-2-2-2	42	7
ADT36 (susceptible check)	90	9
ADT31 (susceptible check)	80	8
TN1 (susceptible check)	90	9
TKM9 (susceptible check)	100	9
IET7492 (resistant check)	8	3

^aOne hundred seedlings/culture inoculated.

Table 2. Serological reaction of RTV-resistant cultures.^a

Selection	Reaction ^b to	
	RTBV	RTSV
IR32429-148-1-3-3	-	-
IR35366-90-3-2-1-2	-	-
IR37865-29-3-1-3	-	-
IR39357-91-3-2-3	+	-
IR50 (resistant check)	+	-
ET7492 (local resistant check)	-	+
TKM9 (susceptible check)	++	++
ADT36 (susceptible check)	+	+++

^aTen seedlings/culture tested. ^b - = no infection, + = low infection, ++ = medium infection, +++ = high infection.

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Field screening for blast (Bl) resistance

M. Suriachandraselvan, J. Venkatakrishnan, K. Nilakantapillai, and T.B. Ranganathan, Rice Research Station, Tirur (CPT) 602025, India

Bl caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is a major disease affecting commonly grown varieties IR50 and TKM9 during Dec-Feb throughout Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu. A severe outbreak occurred during 1985-86.

To identify a resistant, high-yielding rice culture for this season, we evaluated 93 rice accessions under nursery conditions when disease pressure was high. Seeds were sown in 1.2- × 3.0-m plots. Diammonium phosphate (DAP), applied at 180 g/plot 10 d after sowing, induced severe incidence of Bl. Disease scoring was done at 30 d after sowing according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Among the cultures or varieties tested, 38 showed resistant reactions of 1-3, 21 had 5, others showed 7-9 (see table). Most of the highly susceptible cultures had IR50 as one parent. □

Reaction of rice accessions to Bl at Tirur, India.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Disease score ^a
BG367-3	BG280-1-2/Ptb 33	1
TM10265	ADT31/IR8	1
TM4865	AC76/IR8	1
DPI 1091/5	IR20/Kannagi	1
IR20	IR262/TKM 6	1
IR52		1
IR54		1
IR62		1
TNAU843136	CO 37/IR8	1
TNAU831549	TNAU1756/Bhavani	1
TNAU831358	CO 37/Pankhari 203	1
TNAU831411	IET2508/TNAU1756	1
TNAU831399	IET6262/CO 37	1
TNAU831434	IET6262/TNAU1756	1
TM8089	Selection from TKM9	3
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	3
TM1304	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
TM1305	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
TM1313	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
TM1314	TKM 9 Mutant (10 kr)	3
CO 34	TN1/CO 29	3
AS25370	ASD1/IRON 207	3
AS28883	TKM9/IR36	3
IR36	IR1561//IR24-4/ <i>O. nivara</i> ///CR94-13	3
IR56		3
IR60		3
TNAU80030	IR30/Babawee// IR2703-1-252	3

Table continued.

Culture or variety	Parentage	Disease score ^a
TNAU80042	R. Heenathi/ R3403-267 ²	3
TNAU801804	CO 41/CO 39	3
TNAU831540	Pankhari 203/IR36	3
TNAU831521	PY2/IR36	3
TNAU831345	CO 37/IR34	3
TNAU831351	CO 37/SLO 16	3
TNAU843062	IET4141/CO 43	3
TNAU843032	CO 41/CO 43	3
TNAU843028	PY1/CO 43	3
TNAU83134	IET2508/TKM9	3
TNAU840337	TKM9/W. Ponni	3
TM4660	ADT3 1/CH46	5
AS13744	ADT3 1/Ratna// ASD8/IR8	5
TM1307	TKM9 Mutant (10 kr)	5
TNAU801790	CO 41/CO 39	5
TKM1	Pisini pureline selection	5
TNAU83077	CO 73/IR50	5
TNAU83054	IR50/TKM9	5
TNAU8306911	IR50/Kannagi	5
TNAU83069/2	IR50/Kannagi	5
TNAU801803	CO 41/CO 39	5
TNAU83104	CO 41/CO 39	5
TNAU83108	TKM9/TNAU658	5
TNAU831520	PY2/IR36	5
TNAU842955	TKM9/W. Ponni	5
TNAU843232	IET6262/CO 37	5
TNAU831541	TNAU1756/Bhavani	5
TNAU2151	IR28/Kannagi	5
TNAU2099	GEB24/IR30	5
TNAU2057	CO 37/IR26	5
TNAU840335	TKM9/W. Ponni	5
TNAU840336	TKM9/W. Ponni	5
TM2011	C22/TKM6//IR50	7
TM2017	C22/TKM6//IR50	7
TM2021	C22/TKM6//IR50	7
TM2022	TKM9/TKM1//ADT36	7
TM2025	TKM9/TKM1//ADT36	7
TM2026	TKM9/TKM1//ADT36	7
TM9400	IR8/Kalinga// IR34/CH1039	7
CO 33	IR8/ADT27	7
TNAU801793	CO 41/CO 39	7
TKM5	Manakattai PLS	7
TKM6	GEB24/CO 18	7
TKM7	Kullakar PLS 1	7
TKM8	TKM6/TN1	7
IR8	Peta/DGWG	7
TNAU80058	IR2061-456-1-55/IR36	7
TNAU2209	CO 33/CO 13	7
TNAU801824	CO 41/CRM13-3241	7
TM1324	TKM 9 Mutant (20 kr)	9
TM1325	TKM 9 Mutant (20 kr)	9
TM1326	TKM 9 Mutant (20 kr)	9
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	9
IR50		9
TM4966	TKM8/ADT9//CR141- 192/IR26	9
Kannagi	IR8/TKM6	9
TKM4	Yerra Sona PLS	9
CO 18	Vellaikar PLS	9
TNAU840193	9426/6/IR50	9
TNAU840198	9426/6/IR50	9
TNAU842805	94-26/6/IR50	9
TNAU831146	20060/2/IR50	9
TNAU2006	CO 13/IR50	9
TNAU831154	CO41/IR50	9
TNAU831126	TNAU2426/2/IR50	9
TNAU840230	CO 41/IR50	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.